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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of non-cognitive factors, specifically peer group influence, academic self-efficacy, achievement motivation, perception of the school psychological environment, and academic engagement, on the academic achievement (CGPA) of undergraduate students. Data were collected from a sample of 245 young adults (145 males, 100 females) aged 18 to 25 years in Dhaka, Bangladesh, using an adapted Bangla questionnaire package. Correlational analyses revealed that these key psychological and environmental variables are significantly interrelated. Descriptive statistics demonstrated significant gender variations: female undergraduates exhibited higher academic achievement, stronger academic engagement, and a more favorable perception of their school environment compared to male counterparts. Furthermore, regression models indicated that the capacity of these non-cognitive factors to predict performance varies by gender, highlighting academic engagement as the most robust predictor of academic success across both groups.

Role of Non-cognitive Factors in Academic Achievement of Undergraduates

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This study explored the role of non-cognitive factors (i.e., peer group influence, academic self-efficacy, achievement motivation, perception of the school psychological environment, academic engagement) on the academic achievement of undergraduates. The sample consisted of 245 young adults (145 males and 100 females) from Dhaka, Bangladesh ranging in age from 18 through 25 years. Bangla translated measures included the Personal Information Form (PIF), peer group influence scale, academic self-efficacy scale, revised achievement motivation scale, perception of the school psychological environment scale, academic engagement scale and students' academic achievement (CGPA). Results showed that key variables were significantly correlated with one another. Descriptive statistics revealed that there is a significant gender difference in academic achievement, perception of school psychological environment and academic engagement. Females were found to be higher achieving, academically more engaged and to have a better perception of school environment. This gender difference was also reflected in the extent in which the factors predicted students' academic achievement. Academic engagement has been found to be an important predictor of academic achievement for both males and females.

Keywords: academic achievement, peer group influence, academic self-efficacy, achievement motivation, perception of school psychological environment

Young adults' academic achievement at undergraduate level is very crucial for their further achievement and success in life. When they, as young adults, make the transition into an undergraduate educational institution, they are in the process of getting involved into new social environment. If the institution fails to meet the psychological needs of students, it may lead to drops in academic motivation, which

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may contribute to diminished school engagement, which in turn lead to poor academic achievement (Wang & Eccles, 2013). Clear understanding about some particular aspects of psychological environment or characteristics of an institution affecting students' academic achievement is of great importance in the field of School Psychology. An active academic engagement is crucial to students' educational success. Students must be keenly engaged with their academic activities in order to acquire the knowledge and skills required for successful careers ahead. Currently, and particularly at the graduate level, student engagement is an explicit goal of many professionals to reduce student boredom and inattention, to reduce high drop-out rate, to reduce overall low academic achievement as well as to ensure quality education as a whole.

In literature, there are numerous non-cognitive factors, other than cognitive factors, like perceived academic context, teacher quality, academic engagement, and peer influences that affect academic achievement. According to previous researches "academic self-efficacy" is also an important predictor of academic achievement (Adeyemo & Torubeli, 2008; Høigaard, Kovač, Øverby, & Haugen, 2014). Self-efficacy refers to self-beliefs about the degree of perceived self-control over future actions. Higher level of academic self-efficacy is important, perhaps even critical, in attaining desired high levels of academic performance. High self-efficacy may increase achievement motivation and academic engagement, which may in turn increase academic achievement.

Like academic self-efficacy, another non-cognitive factor that is important in students' academic achievement is "peer group influences". Peer can influence everything from what they choose to wear to whether or not they engage in other delinquent behavior. Peers have also a significant influence on students' day to day behavior and feelings, including how much they value school, how well they perform in class, and so on (Adeyemo & Torubeli, 2008).

While cognitive factors like memory, verbal abilities and aptitude for reasoning remain important in this area, the teaching community is starting to realize the importance of non-cognitive factors such as academic environment as well as academic engagement. In fact, it has emerged over the years that these factors are equally important for learning. Therefore, with the ongoing movement to ensure quality education, it is important investigating the impact of non-cognitive factors on academic achievement in Bangladesh as no empirical study attempted such investigation.

The general objective of the present study was to investigate whether the non-cognitive factors like students' the perception of school psychological environment,

academic self-efficacy, peer influence, achievement motivation, and academic engagement significantly associated with students' academic achievement. The specific research objectives were-

1. To investigate whether the student's perception of school psychological environment, academic self-efficacy, peer influence, achievement motivation, academic engagement, and academic achievement are significantly correlated with one another.
2. To investigate whether the student's perception of school psychological environment, academic self-efficacy, peer influence, achievement motivation and academic engagement are significant predictors of academic achievement.
3. To investigate whether the student's perception of school psychological environment, academic self-efficacy, and peer influence are significant predictors of achievement motivation and academic engagement.

Methods

Sample

Data was collected from 245 university students (40.8% women and 59.2% men) in Bangladesh. The mean age of the respondents was 22.16 years ($SD = 1.406$), with a range of 18 through 25 years. They were selected by employing convenience sampling technique namely purposive-incident. Participants were selected from 4 public universities in Dhaka district of Bangladesh and their level of education ranges from 2nd year through masters. Most of the participants (65.3%) were from middle class family background.

Measures

All participants in this research responded to the following self-report questionnaires along with the demographic form. Two pilot testing have been conducted before the field test. In the first pilot testing, alpha coefficients of five scales ranged from 0.58 to 0.85 and in the second one, it ranged from 0.58 to 0.88. The questionnaires were administered in the following sequence:

The Personal Information Form (PIF). The PIF elicited demographic, personal, and social information about respondent's gender, age, grade in university, number of siblings, birth order, family size, parental education, parental occupation, family socioeconomic status, types of family etc.

Peer Group Influence questionnaire (PGI). The *Peer Group Influence Assessment Questionnaire* (Uzezi & Deya, 2017) with 15-items was translated into Bangla and

used to measure peer influence on students. The questionnaire consists of five point scale as follows: Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD). The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.74. A sample item of this scale is “I and my friends compete for good grades”. This scale has 4 items (i.e., 3, 5, 12, and 15) that required reverse scoring.

Academic Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (ASE). The *Academic Self-efficacy Scale* (Roeser, Midgley, & Urdan, 1996) was translated into Bangla and used to measure students’ academic self-efficacy. The scale’s six items assess whether students believe they could master the academic material and skills if they were provided sufficient time and exerted sufficient effort. An item example follows: “If I have enough time, I can do a good job on all my schoolwork.” The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.81. It is a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (not at all true of me) to 5 (very true of me). Thus, higher values indicate higher levels of academic self-efficacy.

Achievement Motivational Beliefs (AMS). 10-item revised *Achievement Motives Scale* (AMS) (Lang & Fries, 2006) was translated into Bangla and used to measure students’ achievement motivation. This scale provides a measure of two salient factors related to achievement motivation namely hope of success and fear of failure. A higher score indicates a higher level of achievement motivation and lower score indicates lower level of achievement motivation. The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.72. Sample item is “I like situations, in which I can find out how capable I am” and responses for each item will be rated on 4-point scales ranging from strongly agree (4) to strongly disagree (1).

School Psychological Environment Scale (SPE). The *School Psychological Environment Scale* (Roeser, Midgley, & Urdan, 1996) was translated into Bangla and used to measure students’ perceptions of the academic contexts. This scale consists of three subscales, two reflecting the goal dimension and one reflecting the relationship dimension. Items were measured on 5-point Likert scales (1 = *not at all true in this school*, 5 = *very true in this school*). The scale measuring student perceptions of a school-task goal structure consists of six items (e.g., “Trying hard counts a lot in this school”) and had an alpha coefficient of 0.72. Items in this scale assess students’ perceptions of an emphasis in the school on effort, understanding, and the belief that all students can learn and be successful. The scale measuring perceptions of school-ability goal structure consists of 5 items (e.g., “In this school, teachers treat kids who get good grades better than other kids”) having an alpha coefficient of 0.80. It includes items tapping student perceptions that relative ability is a salient marker of success in the school, and that higher achieving students are treated better than other students. The teacher-student relationship scale is composed

of 5 items ($\alpha = .88$) and measures student perceptions of the quality of teacher-student relationship in school (e.g., “In this school, teachers treat students with respect”).

Academic Engagement Scale (AES). The Academic Engagement scale consists of three subscales. The Bangla translation of this scale was used to assess the three dimensions of student engagement.

The Behavioral Engagement Scale (Finn & Voelkl, 1993) consists of items from the Attentiveness subscale and items from the School Compliance subscale. The three-item subscale Attentiveness measures the extent to which students report being distracted in classes and have trouble getting schoolwork done. A sample item is “How often do you get schoolwork done on time?” Some items for this indicator were reverse coded, so that higher scores indicated a higher level of attentiveness. The five-item scale School Compliance, describes the levels to which students engage in misconduct in school. A sample item is “How often have you skipped class?” Responses for both of the scales were rated along a 5-point scale, ranging from 1 (almost never) to 5 (almost always). The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.63.

The Emotional Engagement Scale (Pintrich, 2000) consists of the School Belonging scale and the Valuing of School Education scale. The three-item scale School Belonging represents the extent to which adolescents feel personally accepted, respected, and supported by adults and peers in school. A sample item is “I feel happy and safe in this school”. The six-item scale Valuing of School Education assesses adolescents’ interest and belief in the importance and relevance of the general goals of education and academic achievement espoused by the school. A sample item is “I often learn a lot from my schoolwork”. Some items for this indicator were reverse coded, so that higher scores indicated higher levels of emotional engagement. Responses for each item in both scales were rated along a 5-point scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.76.

The scale of *Cognitive Engagement* (Skinner & Wellborn, 1994) consists of Self-Regulated Learning scale and the Cognitive Strategy Use scale. The four-item scale Self-Regulated Learning represents adolescents’ perceived ability of self-monitoring and evaluation. A sample item is “How often do you try to learn from your mistakes?” The four-item scale Cognitive Strategy Use measures adolescents’ perceived use of strategic approach to learning. A sample item is “How often do you try to relate what you are studying to other things you know about?” Responses for each item in both of the scales were rated along a 5-point scale, ranging from 1

(almost never) to 5 (almost always). For this scale, higher score indicates higher level of cognitive engagement. The alpha coefficient for the scale is 0.66.

Academic Achievement Measures. Academic achievement was measured by asking students to report their C/GPA obtained in the most recent examination.

Procedures

For main data acquisition, standard data collection procedure was followed. For taking consent at the beginning, each participant was briefed about the general purpose of the study and assured that their responses would be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. Participants were given a general instruction verbally of how to respond before going through the items on the scale. Before going through the items they were asked to provide general demographic information (e.g., age, gender, CGPA, socioeconomic status, etc.) Also further clarifications were done whenever they faced any problems to understand the items. It took 15 minutes on an average to complete the task.

Results

In order to test gender difference in perception of school psychological environment, academic self-efficacy, peer influence, achievement motivation, academic engagement, and academic achievement, independent sample *t* tests were calculated. Results of *t* tests shown in Table 1 reveal significant gender difference in academic achievement, perceived school psychological environment and academic engagement. Further inspection of Table 1 shows that there is no significant difference between male and female in academic self-efficacy, peer group influence, achievement motivation.

Simple correlation between six major variables were calculated. Table 2 shows that perception of school psychological environment, academic self-efficacy, peer group

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Gender Differences in Major Variables

Variables	Male (<i>n</i> = 145)		Female (<i>n</i> = 100)		<i>t</i>
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Academic achievement	3.21	0.32	3.41	0.30	-4.86
Peer group influence	50.99	8.64	52.92	7.18	-1.84
Academic self-efficacy	22.33	4.04	21.39	4.55	1.70
Achievement motivation	32.79	2.92	32.79	3.24	0.01
School psychological environment	51.88	11.86	56.88	10.30	-2.95
Academic engagement	81.74	9.98	88.10	8.89	-5.12

influence, achievement motivation, academic engagement, and academic achievement are significantly positively correlated with one another. That is, the more supportive and fair the participants perceived their school psychological environment to be, the higher their CGPA was ($r = .16, p < .01$). The more they had been positively influenced by their peer group ($r = .36, p < .01$), the higher academic self-efficacy they had ($r = .19, p < .01$), the more achievement motivation they have ($r = .17, p < .01$) and the more academic engagement they had ($r = .33, p < .01$), the higher their CGPA was.

Results also show that peer group influence was significantly correlated with academic self-efficacy ($r = .27, p < .01$), achievement motivation ($r = .21, p < .01$),

Table 2. Simple Correlations among Major Variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
Academic achievement	1					
Peer group influence	.36**	1				
Academic self-efficacy	.19**	.27**	1			
Achievement motivation	.17**	.21**	.26	1		
School psychological environment	.16*	.43**	.14*	-.01	1	
Academic engagement	.33**	.53**	.38**	.18**	.50**	1

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

perceived school psychological environment ($r = .43, p < .01$) and academic engagement ($r = .53, p < .01$). Again, academic engagement is also significantly correlated with academic self-efficacy ($r = .38, p < .01$), achievement motivation ($r = .18, p < .01$) and perceived school psychological environment ($r = .50, p < .01$). Academic self-efficacy is also significantly correlates with perceived school psychological environment ($r = .14, p < .01$). Because there was a significant gender difference in three of the variables, all further analyses were performed for male and female separately.

Table 3. Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Academic achievement of male (n=145) and female (n=100) participants

Variables	Male		Female	
	<i>B</i>	β	<i>B</i>	β
Peer group influence	.01	.38***	.01	.22*
Academic self-efficacy	.003	.03	.02	.33**
School psychological environment	.00	-.02	-.004	-.13
<i>R</i> ²	.148***		.176***	

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

In order to find out the contributions of the predictor variables (e.g., peer group influence, academic self-efficacy and perception of school psychological environment) to the academic achievement of male and female participants separately, we performed multiple regression analysis. Results presented in Table 3 shows that for male participants, peer group influence ($\beta = .38, p < .001$) made a significant contribution to the variance of academic achievement. This predictor accounted 14.8% variance in academic achievement of male participants. Academic self-efficacy and perception of school psychological environment did not contribute significantly to the variance of their academic achievement. For female participants, academic self-efficacy ($\beta = .33, p < .01$), and peer group influence ($\beta = .22, p < .05$) significantly contributed to the variance of academic achievement and they jointly accounted 17.6% variance in female participants' academic achievement, but perception of school psychological environment failed to make a significant contribution to the variance in academic achievement of female participants.

As depicted in Table 4, for male participants, peer group influence and perception of school psychological environment do not contribute significantly to the variance of achievement motivation. But, 14% variance in achievement

Table 4. Predicting achievement motivation of male (n=145) and female (n=100) participants

Variables	Male		Female	
	<i>B</i>	β	<i>B</i>	β
Peer group influence	.05	.16	.10	.23*
Academic self-efficacy	.21	.29***	.12	.17
School psychological environment	.002	.01	-.10	-.32**
<i>R</i> ²	.14***		.13**	

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

motivation of male participants could be explained by the variation of their academic self-efficacy. For female participants, academic self-efficacy does not contribute significantly to the variance of achievement motivation; and peer group influence and perception of school psychological environment jointly contributed 13% to the total variance of achievement motivation.

As shown in Table 5, peer group influence, academic self-efficacy and perception of school psychological environment jointly accounted 48% variance in academic engagement of male participants. On the other hand, peer group influence and academic self-efficacy jointly accounted 38% variance in academic engagement of female participants. But, perception of school psychological environment failed

to make a significant independent contribution to the variance in academic engagement of female participants.

Table 6 shows that, achievement motivation and academic engagement jointly accounted 13% variance in academic achievement of male participants. But, as depicted in Table 6, only 6% of the variance of female participants' academic

Table 5. Predicting academic engagement of male (n=145) and female (n=100) participants

Variables	Male		Female	
	<i>B</i>	β	<i>B</i>	β
Peer group influence	.37	.32***	.38	.30**
Academic self-efficacy	.67	.27***	.71	.36***
School psychological environment	.30	.36***	.14	.16
<i>R</i> ²	.48***		.38***	

p* < .01; *p* < .001

achievement could be explained with their academic engagement and their achievement motivation failed to make a significant contribution to it.

Discussion

The present study was designed to explore the non-cognitive factors affecting academic achievement of undergraduates. The results of this study suggest that the

Table 6. Predicting academic achievement of male (n=145) and female (n=100) participants

Variables	Male		Female	
	<i>B</i>	β	<i>B</i>	β
Achievement motivation	.03	.26**	-.002	-.02
Academic engagement	.01	.19*	.01	.23*
<i>R</i> ²	.13***		.06**	

p* < .05; *p* < .01; ****p* < .001

academic achievement of both male and female is significantly correlated with peer group influence, academic self-efficacy, achievement motivation, perceived school psychological environment and academic engagement.

The results of this present study reveal that peer group influence is a significant predictor of academic engagement as well as academic achievement regardless of the gender of the participants. This finding is in agreement with Kindermann (1993) who found that peer group influence is crucial for students' engagement in learning activities. Results from the analyses showed that peer influence in academic value

exerted significant effects on young adults' academic engagement that eventually predict their academic achievement. The implication based on the results is that perceived cooperation from peers can motivate students to develop a sense of competency which positively affect their future behavior related to academic activities in the long term. It is, therefore, judicious to conclude that peer group influence may have a noticeable impact on students' academic achievement.

Along with peer influence, academic self-efficacy is also found to be a strong predictor of academic engagement both for male and female and also affects young adults' academic outcomes. Again, all of these three factors are also positively correlated with perception of school psychological environment according to our findings. That is, students who reported more positive perception of school psychological environment also reported the feelings of academic engagement and also felt academically more efficacious. These results corroborate previous research by Roeser and Midgley (1996). Students' perceptions of the teacher and peer environment is predictive of future adaptations. Students who feel that teachers in their institution are less supportive, less caring and emphasizing relative ability become less motivated to work and engage academically (Wang & Holcombe, 2010).

Achievement motivation of students' also plays a significant role in academic engagement and directly and indirectly predict academic achievement. Because motivation is a strong correlate of engagement and might lead to engagement, motivation is where teachers need to begin. Students are motivated to academically engage themselves when they feel interested or have a real purpose for doing so. So motivation to engage is a must for improving academic skill and outcome. However, institutions where teachers are not concerned enough about students' needs for choice, autonomy support, purpose and encouragement, students there might perceive the classroom environment negatively. As a result, there will be diminished motivation and academic engagement.

In our present study, significant gender difference was found in under graduates' academic achievement, perception of school psychological environment and academic engagement. In our society, males and females often differ in their patterns of development and types of socialization which, in turn, shapes their perceptions of school psychological environment. Research has suggested that males perceive school environments as less satisfactory than do females as a result of bias for expectations and actions that favor females (Wang, 2009; Way, Reddy, & Rhodes, 2007). In terms of gender difference, we found that females reported better perception of school psychological environment, academic engagement, and

academic achievement than did males. It is likely that social expectations placed upon females are more parallel to those placed upon “good” students than being the expectations placed on males (Samdal, Nutbeam, Wold, & Kannas, 1998). Generally, good students are expected to be focused, achievement oriented, cooperative with teachers, and confident about communicating and reading skills. These characteristics match more strongly with traditional female gender roles and diverge from traditional male gender roles. Thus, males may face more trouble meeting the expectations of teachers; in turn, their troubles may result in further negative perceptions about the academic environment and lead to a reduced amount of engagement.

Female students’ higher achievement can also be explained in the light of current women empowerment in Bangladesh. In recent years, there have been increased political empowerment for women, better job prospects, improved education and the adoption of new laws to protect their rights. Bangladesh has already achieved gender-parity in primary education. The education of females up to grade XII in public institutions is free and to reduce their dropout rates, stipends are awarded. This upbeat strategy for females’ education resulted in gender parity. For example, female enrollment in primary and in secondary schools is greater than that of males. These flows of women empowerment might have an influence on females’ academic engagement and thus making them higher achiever than males.

However, several limitations of this study need to be noted that might have precluded us from obtaining more expected findings. Data in our present study was obtained using self-report measurement. There is a possibility that students may be influenced by social demands while responding, thus introducing bias into the results. We also did not have a sufficiently large sample to explore important socio-demographic variables and other psychological characteristics that might have contributed to our findings. Again, there might be some unknown factors that caused the difference between male and female students in the extent predicting academic achievement from the five non-cognitive factors. Further research should be conducted to explain the inter-correlations among the factors more rigorously.

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